

1 **The role of waves and heat exchange in the**
2 **hydrodynamics of multi-basin bays: the example of**
3 **Cádiz Bay (Southern Spain)**

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9 **Key Points:**

- 10 • Baroclinic gradients and tidal, wind and waves stresses are used to assess the role
11 of waves and density variations in the hydrodynamics
12 • A Spanish bay is used to explore the results for bays with multiple basins rang-
13 ing between open low frictional to narrow highly frictional
14 • Non-dimensional momentum balance analysis and EOF techniques are employed
15 based on the results of a tested numerical model

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Abstract

Multi-basin bays constitute one of the most complex coastal environments, as tides, waves, freshwater discharges and air-water heat exchange often coexist in basins with very different characteristics, ranging from low-friction open water bodies directly connected to the open sea to narrow, highly frictional shallow creek systems with no connection to the open sea. Although the influence of tides and baroclinic gradients in these areas is relatively well known, the role of waves in the hydrodynamics and distributions of density, salinity and temperature has received less attention. The aim of this research is to evaluate the effects of waves and heat exchange on the hydrodynamics of multiple basins through numerical modeling. The model is calibrated and tested in a mesotidal bay in Southern Spain with five different basins; the results are used to analyze the momentum balance equation and the salinity, temperature and density distributions for simulations with and without consideration of waves. The results show that baroclinic density gradients often dominate the hydrodynamics in highly frictional, shallow basins of the bay where the air-water heat exchange is more efficient. Waves can also modify the hydrodynamics of basins directly connected to open sea by increasing flow velocities and causing deviations of baroclinic density gradients, increasing the importance of tidal stresses in low frictional basins, while increasing baroclinic density gradients in narrow, highly frictional basins.

Plain Language Summary

Bays with multiple basins are very complex coastal systems in which a multitude of agents coexist and interact differently in each basin. Among these agents, tides, waves, wind, freshwater discharges and air-water heat exchange are the main responsible for the hydrodynamics and biogeochemistry of the bay. Although the influence of wind and tides is well studied, the role played by waves and heat exchange, the latter characterized by variations in salinity, temperature and density, has not been studied in depth. In this work, numerical modeling is used to improve the understanding of these roles in bays with basins ranging from large bodies of water directly connected to the open sea, to narrow channel systems where friction is predominant. The model has been applied to a 5-basin bay located in southern Spain. The results show that the effects derived from changes in water density dominate in basins formed by shallow channels due to the efficiency of heat exchange. Waves dominate in areas close to the open sea by increasing current velocities and modifying water density. However, although waves are able to influence the hydrodynamics of these areas, variations in salinity and temperature do not alter the biogeochemical conditions of the bay.

1 Introduction

Bays are semi-enclosed bodies of water connected to the open ocean that are formed by one or more basins with different hydrodynamic behaviors (Arheimer et al., 2015). The presence of multiple basins increases the complexity of these coastal systems from a hydrodynamic and management point of view. For example, basins near the open ocean are usually more exposed to waves (Zarzuelo, D'Alpaos, et al., 2019), which can control their hydrodynamics during storms. However, the hydrodynamics of inner basins may be driven only by wind, tides and/or baroclinic flows that are mainly triggered by solar radiation and stratification, since river discharges of fresh water can be usually negligible in bays, such as the bays of San Francisco (Elias & Hansen, 2012) and Chesapeake (Xu et al., 2012) in USA, or the Cádiz Bay (Zarzuelo et al., 2015) in Spain, in contrast to alluvial estuaries (Savenije, 2005; Díez-Minguito et al., 2012, 2013; Serrano et al., 2020). Consequently, inner basins have historically been used as natural harbors where infrastructures such as breakwaters or bridges, among others, have been developed with the consequent impact on the hydrodynamics, salinity and temperature distributions.

66 In addition, the biogeochemical characteristics of bays are often affected by tidal
67 processes, river discharges and variations in seawater temperature due to the air-water
68 heat exchange (Burdige, 2006). These processes, as well as water exchange, sediment trans-
69 port and environmental conditions are triggered by residual or subtidal flows (Zarzuelo,
70 López-Ruiz, D’Alpaos, et al., 2018) which in turn are mainly driven by density gradi-
71 ents, tides, winds and waves (Valle-Levinson et al., 2018). The relative importance of
72 each driver can be very different from one basin to another due to the particular geom-
73 etry of the bay and the atmospheric and maritime conditions (Zarzuelo, D’Alpaos, et al.,
74 2019). Furthermore, their relative role can also vary over time due to the stochastic be-
75 havior of wind and waves, and the impact of the construction of new infrastructures (Zarzuelo,
76 López-Ruiz, D’Alpaos, et al., 2018; Zarzuelo, López-Ruiz, & Ortega-Sánchez, 2019).

77 To assess the relative roles of tidal stresses, baroclinic density gradients and wind
78 stresses, Valle-Levinson and Schettini (2016) and Juarez et al. (2019) introduced the non-
79 dimensional analysis of the tide-averaged depth-integrated momentum balance equation
80 using field data. With this analysis, the authors defined three non-dimensional numbers
81 relating the flow drivers and the forcings modifying the flow in a tropical mesotidal es-
82 tuary and a microtidal bay, respectively. However, to the author’s knowledge a similar
83 approach has not been used to assess the relative role of wave stresses on the hydrody-
84 namics of estuaries and bays.

85 Using a different approach, Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOF, Emery and Thom-
86 son (2001)) have been used to identify the main modes of spatial and temporal varia-
87 tion of environmental variables such as salinity and temperature and their relation with
88 hydrodynamics, since EOF modes can be associated with different dynamic mechanisms
89 despite their empirical nature. This method has been applied to analyze the formation
90 of salt-plugs in bays (Juarez et al., 2019) or internal tides in fjords (Ross et al., 2014).
91 However, despite its relevance to the dynamics of bays, there is little observational or
92 numerical evidence of the relative role of the different drivers that trigger the circula-
93 tion of the estuary and its biogeochemical processes (Xu et al., 2012).

94 Numerical models are an efficient and flexible alternative for analyzing hydrody-
95 namics in complex coastal systems such as multi-basin bays, as they can model longer
96 periods of time with any range of maritime and atmospheric conditions (Cornett et al.,
97 2013). The spatio-temporal coverage of the simulations can be used to extend the re-
98 sults of the analysis of the momentum balance equation and the EOF techniques. In ad-
99 dition, the effects of some forcings, such as waves, can be easily isolated by excluding them
100 from the simulations. These characteristics were used by a significant number of researchers
101 to analyze the relative roles of the forcings triggering the hydrodynamics of estuaries and
102 bays (Kukulka et al., 2017; Kumbier et al., 2018), coastal shelves and the wave-current
103 interactions therein (Apotsos et al., 2008; Hansen et al., 2015; Hopkins et al., 2016; Chegini
104 et al., 2018) and also to study the temperature, salinity and density variations in estu-
105 aries or bays (Elshorbagy et al., 2013; Wang & Sheng, 2016; Zhang et al., 2018). How-
106 ever, the impact of waves on the hydrodynamics and the distribution of salinity and tem-
107 perature in bays has received much less attention from researchers.

108 The objective of this work is to analyze the role of waves and air-water heat ex-
109 change in the hydrodynamics and the distributions of density, salinity and temperature
110 of bays composed of two or more basins that show different hydrodynamic behavior. The
111 analysis is carried out by means of calibrated and tested numerical modeling of hydro-
112 dynamics, salinity and temperature in a multi-basin bay (Cádiz Bay, Southern Spain).
113 Numerical simulations during a complete year are used to perform (1) a non-dimensional
114 analysis of the momentum balance along a transect across the bay; and (2) an EOF anal-
115 ysis. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2.1 presents the study site and the field
116 data employed, Section 2.2 describes the numerical model and its calibration and test-
117 ing, with Section 2.3 summarizing how the non-dimensional and EOF analyses are made.

118 Section 3 presents the main results obtained and their discussion, whereas Section 4 sum-
 119 marizes the main conclusions found.

120 2 Materials and methods

121 2.1 Field site and observations

122 2.1.1 Field site

123 The Cádiz Bay is a $7 \cdot 10^7$ m², marsh-dominated, coastal plain estuary in Southern
 124 Spain ($36^\circ 31'N$, $6^\circ 17'W$, Fig. 1). The tides are mainly semidiurnal with tidal ranges be-
 125 tween 2 and 4 m, maximum tidal currents above 1.5 m/s (Zarzuolo et al., 2015) and a
 126 mean tidal prism of $2 \cdot 10^6$ m³ (Zarzuolo et al., 2017). The bay is composed of three well-
 127 defined open basins: outer basin, constriction and inner basin (A, B and C, respectively,
 128 in Fig. 1a), and two creek systems.

129 The inner basin is characterized by gentle slopes and an average depth of 8 m. At
 130 low tide, 50% of its surface is above sea level, exposing low-lying mudflats cut by deep
 131 tidal channels. It has a double connection to open sea by (1) two systems of creeks (Car-
 132 racas and Sancti-Petri Creeks, Fig. 1a) with intertidal flats around the fringes, subti-
 133 dal flats (up to 2 m deep) and tidal channels (6-8 m deep) discharging into the Atlantic
 134 Ocean across Sancti-Petri creeks (Zarzuolo, D'Alpaos, et al., 2019); and (2) the constric-
 135 tion and the outer basin.

136 The constriction (B, Fig. 1a) is an 18 km long channel SE-NW oriented, with an
 137 average width of 1.3 km and maximum depths of 18 m. This area is where the major-
 138 ity of the human interventions were developed (Fig. 1b; Zarzuolo et al. (2015, 2020)),
 139 modifying the ecosystem of the bay (Llope, 2016) and causing the migration of many species
 140 (Hobbs et al., 2009). Finally, the outer basin (A, Fig. 1a) has an average depth of 15 m
 141 and is connected to the open sea directly through its western boundary.

142 Wind conditions (data from Buoy 2342 for the period 1998-2013, Puertos del Es-
 143 tado, Spanish Ministry of Public Works; Fig. 1e) are stronger and predominantly north-
 144 westerly from January to April due to prevailing westerlies from the Atlantic Ocean. Sea-
 145 breeze is observed from July to September, when weaker winds come from highly vari-
 146 able directions. Wave data from the same buoy (Fig. 1d) indicate that waves propagate
 147 predominantly from the West and Southeast. The 50%, 90% and 99% exceedance sig-
 148 nificant wave heights (H_s) in deep water are 1 m, 2 m and 3.4 m, respectively. During
 149 extreme storms, maximum H_s typically exceed 3.8 m.

150 2.1.2 Field data

151 Data from two field surveys were used to calibrate and validate the numerical model.
 152 Both surveys measured water levels, currents, salinity and temperature using ADCPs
 153 (acoustic doppler current profilers) and CTs (conductivity-temperature) devices deployed
 154 at the same locations simultaneously. ADCPs measured pressure and orbital velocity with
 155 an averaging interval of 120 s for a final profile interval of 900 s, while CTs recorded tem-
 156 perature and salinity every 15 min 1 m above the seafloor. The sampling period for the
 157 first field survey was from December 22, 2011 to April 18, 2012, and the instruments were
 158 located at I_1 , I_2 and I_3 (Fig. 1b, Zarzuolo et al. (2015)). The second field survey was car-
 159 ried out from May 24 to August 29, 2013 to evaluate the water exchange between the
 160 outer and inner basin, with the instruments deployed at I_3 , I_{3a} and I_{3b} (Fig. 1b, Zarzuolo,
 161 López-Ruiz, and Ortega-Sánchez (2018)).

Figure 1. a) Location of study site. b) Detail of the area where the CT stations were deployed (circles and crosses correspond to the first and second field survey, respectively). c) Location of the buoy 2342 and boundaries of the numerical model grid (blue dashed line). The black rectangle represents the area showed in panel a). Wave (d) and wind (e) roses at the study site.

2.2 Numerical model

2.2.1 Model description and setup

The 4.02.03 version of the Delft3D numerical model (Lesser et al., 2004) was used to simulate depth-averaged density and wave driven flows, wave propagation and salinity and temperature distributions in Cádiz Bay. The use of depth-averaged simulations was chosen as the stratification effects in the bay are negligible (Alvarez et al., 1999; González-García et al., 2018) and it significantly reduces the computational costs. The hydrodynamic module of the model was used to solve the two-dimensional depth-averaged Shallow Water Equations (SWE), the advection-diffusion equation for the transport of salt and heat and an equation of state to calculate the water density. For the generation and propagation of waves within the model domain, the SWAN model (Booij et al., 1999; Ris et al., 1999) included in the Delft3D distribution was implemented. This is a spectral wave model that solves the action balance equation considering the wave-current interactions. This model simulates wind wave generation and energy dissipation due to white-capping, depth-induced wave breaking and bottom friction. Both modules (hydrodynamics and wave propagation) are coupled online during the simulations: water levels and currents are considered for the wave propagation processes, while wave-induced forces are included in the momentum equation of the hydrodynamic module. Among the available heat exchange models within Delft3D, the *ocean* heat flux model (Gill, 1982; Lane, 1989) was used as it was found to be the most balanced option considering the dimensions of the bay and the temporal scale of the analysis (1 year). This model considers the relative humidity, air temperature, cloud coverage, shortwave solar radiation, light attenuation (Secchi depth), and the Dalton and Stanton numbers, the latter two being used as calibration parameters.

Modeling frameworks based on the model described above have been successfully applied to many coastal and estuarine regions (Elias & Hansen, 2012). In particular, previous studies used it to analyze the hydrodynamics of the Cádiz Bay and the influence of human interventions on water exchange, residual currents and tidal distortion (Zarzuelo et al., 2015, 2017; Zarzuelo, López-Ruiz, D’Alpaos, et al., 2018). However, environmental variables such as salinity and temperature, and the influence of waves on the hydrodynamics of the bay, have not yet been modeled or analyzed.

In this work, the Delft3D scheme used in Zarzuelo et al. (2015, 2017); Zarzuelo, López-Ruiz, D’Alpaos, et al. (2018) is modified to include the effect of waves, salt and heat transport. The bathymetric data were provided by the Instituto Hidrográfico de la Marina (Spanish Ministry of Defense) with a spatial resolution of $10 \times 10 \text{ m}^2$, while the detailed multibeam bathymetry of the area near the city of Cádiz was provided by the Port Authority of Cádiz. The topography was obtained from the Digital Elevation Model of the Andalusian Regional Government with the same resolution as the bathymetry. The model grid is curvilinear, covering the entire bay and the continental shelf close to the study site (boundaries shown in Fig. 1c). This grid has a variable size ranging from $20 \times 20 \text{ m}^2$ at the offshore boundaries to $4 \times 4 \text{ m}^2$ at the Carracas and Sancti-Petri creeks (Fig. 1a), where the grid was refined for this particular study to capture in more detail the circulation between the inner bay and the open ocean through these shallow areas. This refinement was also used to reduce the inaccuracies of the drying/flooding modeling (threshold depth of 0.1 m) at these shallower areas, where the intertidal zones are proportionally larger.

The initial conditions for the simulations were defined as water at rest and salinity and temperature values of 36.5 psu and 15°C , respectively within the complete model domain. After different tests with the model, the simulated period used for the spin-up interval was one month. For the model boundary conditions, the eighteen main tidal harmonics (M2, S2, SA, Q1, O1, P1, K1, 2N2, MU2, N2, NU2, L2, T2, R2, K2, MN4, M4, MS4) obtained from the model Oregon State Tidal Prediction (Egbert & Erofeeca, 2002)

214 were used as the astronomical forcing (water levels) at the offshore boundary. The wa-
 215 ter inputs from the San Pedro and Guadalete rivers were included as freshwater sources
 216 (Fig. 1a), using their annual averaged discharges (including also their averaged temper-
 217 ature and salinity conditions) due to their low inflow rates and variability because of the
 218 river regulations (Zarzuelo et al., 2020). The data for these discharges were provided by
 219 the Andalusian Regional Government. For the air/water heat exchange, spatially-uniform
 220 daily-averaged data of solar radiation, air temperature and humidity and cloudiness were
 221 obtained from the Andalusian Regional Government. Finally, wind and wave data with
 222 3h-interval were obtained from Buoy 2342 (Puertos del Estado, Spanish Ministry of Pub-
 223 lic Works, Fig. 1c). The former were used as forcings for the hydrodynamic and wave
 224 propagation modules, while the latter were defined as spectral boundary conditions for
 225 the wave propagation module. In addition, 3h-interval boundary transport conditions
 226 of salinity and temperature from this buoy were used to solve the advection-diffusion equa-
 227 tion of the model.

228 **2.2.2 Model calibration and testing**

229 The model was calibrated and tested for hydrodynamics (water levels and currents),
 230 salinity and temperature. For the hydrodynamics, the same procedure described by Zarzuelo
 231 et al. (2015) was repeated in order to check if the refinement of the grid over the creeks
 232 had any impact on the model’s ability to reproduce water levels and currents. This in-
 233 cludes a calibration period with 15-minute data using the first field survey from January
 234 4th to 22th (2012) and a testing period with 3h data from the second field survey from
 235 May 24th to June 10th (2013). The first period was chosen due to atmospheric condi-
 236 tions characterized by low wind velocities and wave heights, whereas the second includes
 237 episodes of high wind speeds and wave heights. The results of the model agreement for
 238 these variables are included in Table 1, where the root mean squared errors (RMSE), cor-
 239 relations (R) and skill coefficients (S) are showed. Considering that M_n and O_n are the
 240 modeled and observed data, respectively, at N discrete points, the RMSE is defined by:

$$\text{RMSE} = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (M_n - O_n)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

241 The correlation coefficient (R) between M_n and O_n is given by:

$$R = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (M_n - \overline{M_n})(O_n - \overline{O_n})}{\sigma_M \sigma_O} \quad (2)$$

242 where σ_M and σ_O are the standard deviations of the modeled and observed data,
 243 respectively. The overbar represents the mean value. The correlation ranges from -1 (anti-
 244 correlation) to 0 (no correlation) up to 1 (total correlation).

245 The Skill coefficient S (Wilmott, 1981), which ranges from 0 (bad skill) to 1 (good
 246 skill), is defined as:

$$S = 1 - \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N |M_n - O_n|^2}{\sum_{n=1}^N |M_n - \overline{O_n}|^2 + |O_n - \overline{O_n}|^2} \quad (3)$$

247 Using these parameters, an excellent agreement for calibration and testing between
 248 the observed and modeled water levels was achieved ($R = 0.99$). The R and skill values
 249 for the calibrated tidal currents (U and V) are lower, but the agreement is still good (R
 250 $= 0.95-0.92$, $S = 0.88-0.64$, Table 1). Although the fit for the testing results is more dem-
 251 anding due to the location of the instruments (shallower areas), according to the clas-

sification proposed by Van Rijn et al. (2003), a good agreement is also obtained with $R = 0.93-0.67$ and $S = 0.91-0.59$ values. The hydrodynamic results for the instrument I_2 were not available due to deployment problems. The wave height of the instrument I_1 is calibrated obtaining in this period a good correlation ($R = 0.51$). The reader is referred to Zarzuelo et al. (2015) and the Supporting Information for further details on the hydrodynamic calibration and testing processes.

The same procedure was followed for salinity and temperature validation. Considering the temporal resolution of solar radiation, cloudiness and atmospheric temperature and humidity (daily scale), calibration and test agreements were obtained both on instantaneous and daily-averaged scales. The results are shown in Supporting Information (Figs. S1 and S2) and Table 1, while the calibrated model parameters are shown in Table S1 of Supporting Information. These values are considered a good fit between the model and the data compared to previous studies (Des et al., 2019).

2.2.3 Model simulations

Two different simulations of approximately one year each (October 2012 to November 2013) were conducted with the calibrated and tested model. The former (S_1) simulated the combined effects of tides, wind and waves on the hydrodynamics and salinity and temperature distributions in Cádiz Bay, whereas the latter (S_2) was used to quantify the role of waves using the same bathymetric, tidal and atmospheric conditions, but disabling the wave propagation module (SWAN model).

2.3 Analysis of the data

To characterize the role of waves in the hydrodynamics of the bay, the results of the simulations were used to scale up terms in the momentum balance and to perform the EOF analysis. Both techniques are described throughout the next sections.

2.3.1 Momentum balance

An analysis based on non-dimensional parameters describing their relative importance was used to assess the influence of tidal stresses, baroclinic density gradients and wind and wave stresses and their differences between the various basins in the bay. These parameters, previously used by a significant number of researchers (i.e., Valle-Levinson and Schettini (2016); Tenorio-Fernandez et al. (2018)), are obtained after scaling a simplified version of the momentum equation in which only the terms used for the analysis are retained. It is worth noting that this equation is used only to obtain the expressions of the non-dimensional parameters, which are then evaluated using the results of the numerical model obtained by considering all the processes described in Section 2.2 and Lesser et al. (2004). This framework allows to contextualize the results since they can be directly compared with those obtained for other areas and methods (i.e. numerical modeling or field data), retaining a reasonable computational cost, in contrast to the post-processing of the complete momentum balance computed by the model.

The terms representing the tidal stresses, baroclinic density gradients and wind and wave stresses in the simplified residual momentum equation were evaluated at a representative location for each basin (Fig. 2). According to (Zarzuelo et al., 2015, 2017), at these locations the flow velocities are oriented parallel to the transect that crosses all the basins on the bay, linking both connections to open sea (Fig. 2). In the following, only the along-transect momentum equation is considered (including both along and across-transect terms) whereas the cross-transect momentum equation is neglected. The effect of the transect curvature is also neglected due to the bay dimensions and the large radius of curvature. Hence, the non-rotational along-transect residual momentum balance, neglecting the Coriolis effects, can be written as (Valle-Levinson & Schettini, 2016):

Table 1. Results for hydrodynamic, temperature and salinity calibration and testing. RMSE refers to root mean squared error, R is correlation and S is skill. Inst. and daily are instantaneous and daily-average values, respectively.

Instrument	I ₁			I ₂			I ₃			I _{3a}			I _{3b}		
	RMSE	R	S	RMSE	R	S	RMSE	R	S	RMSE	R	S	RMSE	R	S
Hydrodynamic calibration	η (m)	0.10	0.99	0.99	-	-	0.11	0.99	0.99	-	-	-	-	-	-
	U (m/s)	0.09	0.92	0.88	-	-	0.14	0.95	0.78	-	-	-	-	-	-
	V (m/s)	0.27	0.94	0.71	-	-	0.38	0.95	0.64	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hydrodynamic testing	η (m)	-	-	-	-	-	0.16	0.99	0.99	0.23	0.98	0.98	0.23	0.99	0.98
	U (m/s)	-	-	-	-	-	0.15	0.88	0.81	0.13	0.93	0.91	0.12	0.67	0.79
	V (m/s)	-	-	-	-	-	0.36	0.88	0.71	0.46	0.84	0.59	0.26	0.76	0.65
Temp / Sal calibration	Temp. inst. (°C)	0.45	0.81	0.67	0.25	0.60	0.58	0.25	0.84	0.79	-	-	-	-	-
	Temp. daily (°C)	0.17	0.91	0.82	0.17	0.77	0.69	0.18	0.76	0.69	-	-	-	-	-
	Sal. inst. (psu)	0.08	0.79	0.78	0.09	0.53	0.52	0.07	0.71	0.56	-	-	-	-	-
	Sal. daily (psu)	0.06	0.84	0.67	0.05	0.72	0.66	0.06	0.82	0.58	-	-	-	-	-
Temp / Sal testing	Temp. inst. (°C)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.13	0.92	0.93	0.14	0.87	0.82	0.13	0.79
	Temp. daily (°C)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.07	0.93	0.94	0.10	0.88	0.83	0.08	0.79
	Sal. inst. (psu)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.05	0.82	0.86	0.02	0.82	0.77	0.03	0.76
	Sal. daily (psu)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.02	0.89	0.92	0.01	0.85	0.79	0.02	0.79

$$U_0 \frac{\partial U_0}{\partial s} + V_0 \frac{\partial U_0}{\partial n} + \overline{\frac{g}{\rho} \int_z^\eta \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial s} dz} = -g \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\nu \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right] + \overline{F_{\text{waves}}} \quad (4)$$

where the overbar denotes tidally averaged quantities, s and n are the along and across-transect directions, U_0 and V_0 are the along and across-transect tidal current amplitudes for each tidal cycle, respectively, ρ is water density, g is gravitational acceleration, η is the deviation of the mean water surface from the still water depth h , z the vertical coordinate and ν is the vertical eddy viscosity. The first two terms in the left-hand side of Eq. (4) account for the tidal stresses, although in this case, as the flow velocities are transect-oriented, the second term (which is proportional to the cross-transect velocities) is neglected. The second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (4) refers to frictional effects (or tidally averaged stress divergence, Tenorio-Fernandez et al. (2018)). In this case, the frictional forces at the surface of the water column are given by the wind stresses. The term $\overline{F_{\text{waves}}}$ accounts for the residual external forces representing the tidally averaged effects of waves over the water column:

$$\overline{F_{\text{waves}}} = \frac{1}{\rho(h + \eta)} \left(\frac{\partial S_{ss}}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial S_{sn}}{\partial n} \right) \quad (5)$$

where the partial derivatives represent the gradients of the radiation stress tensor S_{ij} (Longuet-Higgins & Stewart, 1962) accounting for the effects of waves. The first two terms on the left-hand side of Eq. (4) are the tidal stresses, and the third term is the baroclinic pressure gradient, which is proportional to the horizontal density gradients. The other flow modifiers appear on the right-hand side, including, in order of appearance, the residual water level slope, the residual vertical stress divergence and the external forces induced by waves.

In Eq. (4), tidal stresses can be scaled as U_0^2/L , where U_0 is the amplitude of the tidal current along the transect for each semidiurnal tidal cycle, and L is the length scale of each basin (the same for density gradients and tides). Five different lengths were obtained as the curvilinear distance between each representative location and the entrance of the ocean tide arriving to the specific location projected over the transect (Fig. 2b). The baroclinic term in Eq. (4) is scaled as $g\Delta\rho h/(\rho_0 L)$, where ρ_0 is the reference density of the water measured at the inlet, $\Delta\rho$ the variation in density between the representative locations and the open sea and h is the averaged water depth for each basin. The surface frictional term in Eq. (4) is scaled as $\tau_w/(\rho_0 h)$, where τ_{wind} is the wind stress, for which the wind velocities are projected along the transect at every location.

Using these scales, the internal tidal Froude number, Fr_0 , (Valle-Levinson & Schettini, 2016) was used to compare the tidal stresses and the baroclinic density gradients, defined as:

$$Fr_0 = \frac{U_0^2/L}{g\Delta\rho h/(\rho_0 L)} = \frac{\rho_0 U_0^2}{\Delta\rho g h} \quad (6)$$

while for the relation between wind and tidal stresses we used the Stress ratio, S_0 , (Tenorio-Fernandez et al., 2018), defined as:

$$S_0 = \frac{U_0^2/L}{\tau_w/(\rho_0 h)} = \frac{\rho_0 h U_0^2}{L \tau_w} \quad (7)$$

To the authors' knowledge, tidal stresses has not been compared to wave stresses in previous works. For that purpose, this investigation proposes a new dimensionless number derived from Eq. (5). Similar to the terms for tidal, baroclinic and wind stresses, the term describing the gradients of the radiation stress tensor can be scaled as $F_s/(\rho_0 h)$, being F_s the along-transect wave-induced force per unit of surface obtained as $\partial S_{ss}/\partial s +$

Parameter	Expression	Definition
Internal tidal Froude number	$Fr_0 = \frac{\rho_0 U_0^2}{\Delta \rho g h}$	Tidal stresses / Baroclinic density gradients
Stress ratio	$S_0 = \frac{\rho_0 h U_0^2}{L \tau_w}$	Tidal stresses / Wind stresses
Wave stress ratio	$S_w = \frac{\rho_0 h U_0^2}{L F_s}$	Tidal stresses / Wave stresses
Wedderburn number	$W = \frac{L \tau_w}{\Delta \rho g h^2}$	Wind stresses / Baroclinic density gradients

Table 2. Summary of non-dimensional numbers for the momentum balance analysis.

343 $\partial S_{sn}/\partial n$ in 3h intervals. The result of this analysis is a dimensionless number so-called
 344 Wave Stress ratio, S_w , defined as:

$$345 \quad S_w = \frac{U_0^2/L}{F_s/(\rho_0 h)} = \frac{\rho_0 h U_0^2}{L F_s} \quad (8)$$

346 Finally, wind stress and baroclinic gradients were compared using the Wedderburn
 347 number, W , (Monismith, 1986) defined as:

$$348 \quad W = \frac{\tau_w/(\rho_0 h)}{g \Delta \rho h/(\rho_0 L)} = \frac{L \tau_w}{\Delta \rho g h^2} \quad (9)$$

349 The hydrodynamic variables defining the four non-dimensional numbers summa-
 350 rized in Table 2 were obtained after tidally averaging and transect-projecting the results
 351 of the numerical model.

352 **2.3.2 Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs)**

353 Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) were used to analyze the main modes of
 354 temporal variation in the depth-averaged salinity and temperature along the bay tran-
 355 sect. The EOFs are obtained using the Principal Component Analysis technique (PCA,
 356 Baquerizo and Losada (2008)) which provides a set of M -dimensional vectors \bar{e}_k , $k \leq$
 357 M (EOFs) which are linear combinations of the salinity or temperature. In the analy-
 358 sis, M represents the number of time steps used. The first EOF explains the maximum
 359 possible variance of the original variables, while the second explains most of the remain-
 360 ing variance and so on. Therefore, by retaining the first p components it is possible to
 361 explain most of the variation of the original variables at each instant considered. The
 362 original salinity or temperature time series can then be approximated as:

$$y(\bar{t}) = \bar{\mu} + Z_1 \bar{e}_1 + \dots + Z_p \bar{e}_p \quad (10)$$

363 being y the salinity/temperature time series at a certain location, \bar{t} the vector contain-
 364 ing the M moments, $\bar{\mu}$ a vector with the mean values of salinity/temperature and (Z_1, \dots, Z_p)
 365 the scores of each EOF, which are also obtained in the analysis. The objective of this
 366 analysis is to relate the EOFs that explain most of the salinity/temperature variance with
 367 the atmospheric and meteorological variables included in the numerical model by eval-
 368 uating their correlation.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Overall hydrodynamic conditions

Although the results for the numerical model are obtained over the complete grid domain (Fig. 1), in this work their analysis is restricted to the transect that crosses all the basins of Cádiz Bay. In addition, to simplify and facilitate interpretation and discussion of the results, five particular locations (stations) are used along this transect at the outer bay, PC, the inner bay, CC and SPC (Fig. 2b). The points that define the transect and the stations are shown in Fig. (2a), where colors indicate the distance from each point to Inlet 1. Fig. (2b) shows a schematization of the Cádiz Bay and the behavior of the ocean tide according to Zarzuelo, D'Alpaos, et al. (2019). The tide enters the bay using two different pathways: through Inlet 1 (connecting the open sea with the outer bay) and through Inlet 2 (connecting the open sea with SPC). Further on, the two waves converge at the boundary between CC and SPC (Zarzuelo, D'Alpaos, et al., 2019).

Density, temperature and salinity distributions along the transect for S_1 are shown in Fig. (3). This figure also represents the humidity, air temperature, solar radiation, rainfall and evaporation data considered for the modeling that were non-dimensionalized with their maximum values. The density distribution shows variations between 1.023 and 1.028 kg/m³ with clear seasonal and fortnightly periodicities. The former is well correlated with solar radiation, air temperature, humidity and evaporation, with higher (lower) water densities during winter (summer). The latter is triggered by the tidal spring/neap cycles: during spring tides the density clearly increases (decreases) in the inner bay and CC during winter (summer), while these variations are less important during neap tides. During autumn and spring density gradients are clearly lower. Therefore, the bay is hypopycnal during winter, as there is an increase in density from the inlets to the inner bay, while hypopycnal conditions occur during summer. These results are consistent with experimental analysis carried out in tropical lagoons, such as Tenorio-Fernandez et al. (2018), where these patterns were identified for the dry and wet seasons, respectively.

The temperature distribution (Fig. 3b) shows very similar trends, being the main responsible of the density variations, as observed for the Yucatán lagoon by Tenorio-Fernandez et al. (2018). In this case the differences are up to 20°C, although the temporal variations at the transect boundaries (open sea) are less important, highlighting the role of air-water heat exchange over the shallower areas of the bay. These seasonal variations in temperature are key for the Cádiz Bay biogeochemistry, since they are closely related to the mineralization processes of the organic matter that are caused by the increase of metabolic rates with temperature, especially in the outer bay (Burgos et al., 2018), and also to the microphytobenthos biomass net production at the inner bay (Haro et al., 2020).

The results for salinity (Fig. 3c) show that variations over the bay are not significant, with differences of up to 1.5 psu. Temporal variations at the two boundaries (Inlet 1 and 2) correspond to the model offshore boundary conditions. If the spatial differences are analyzed, three different areas can be identified: the outer bay (0-8 km), Puntales channel and inner bay (8-19 km) and the Carracas and Sancti-Petri creeks (19-40 km). The general trend shows that salinity is higher in the outer bay and in the two creeks systems, while minimum values are found at the intermediate area (Puntales channel and inner bay), specifically in the connection between the outer bay and PC (\simeq 8 km). This point corresponds approximately to the location of the two freshwater inputs modeled (Guadalete and San Pedro rivers, see Fig. 2b). These freshwater discharges reduce the salinity in this area as they are confined to the outer bay due to two vortices that lead the flow from the northern part of the outer bay towards PC (Zarzuelo et al., 2017). Although the dynamics of the outer bay may explain the spatial variations in salinity, it does not provide any information on its temporal distribution, since freshwater discharges were considered constant during the year.

Figure 2. Field site schematization: a) Transect along the bay and location of the stations at the outer bay (Outer), Puntales channel (PC), inner bay (Inner), Carracas creeks (CC) and Sancti-Petri creeks (SPC). The colors of the points indicate the distance to the main bay inlet in the outer bay. b) Schematization of the basins of the bay. The arrows indicate the direction of the ocean tide during flooding, while the black cross indicates the location of the ocean tide convergence.

Figure 3. Density (a), salinity (b) and temperature (c) distributions along the bay transect. Horizontal and vertical axes represent date and distance to Inlet 1, respectively. Panel d) shows the non-dimensional humidity (W, blue), air temperature (T_{air} , red), solar radiation (R, yellow), rainfall (P, purple) and evaporation (E, green).

420 The EOF analysis was used to quantify the role of climate variables in salinity and
 421 temperature distributions. Fig. (4a1-a3) shows the results for the first EOF (\bar{e}_1 , Eq. 10)
 422 for temperature. This EOF explains 94% of the variation of the original variable; the com-
 423 parison of the reconstruction of the data series $y(\bar{t}) = \bar{\mu} + Z_1\bar{e}_1$ (Fig. 4a1) with the
 424 original data (Fig. 3b) shows that the main trends are retained. Correlations between
 425 the scores Z_1 and the climate variables were analyzed, and the highest value was found
 426 for the air temperature ($R = 0.86$). Both the scores and the air temperature are rep-
 427 resented in Fig. (4c), showing that they are closely related, but with a time lag between
 428 them.

429 The results for salinity are shown in Fig. (4b1-b3). In this case, the first EOF ex-
 430 plains 89% of the variability of the original variable, preserving also its trends (Figs. 4b1
 431 and 3c). According to the processes described above, the first EOF shows its maximum
 432 absolute values at the connection between the outer bay and PC, thereby highlighting
 433 the importance of the outer bay vortices in the spatial distribution of salinity, which is
 434 common in a salt-plug system. In terms of temporal variations, maximum and minimum
 435 values of Z_1 are found during summer and spring, respectively. The best correlation was
 436 found for evaporation ($R = 0.75$), which may explain the temporal variations in salin-
 437 ity.

438 For the analysis of the momentum equation, the logarithm to base 10 of the non-
 439 dimensional numbers defined in table 2 was used, with positives (negatives) values in-
 440 dicating a greater importance of the numerator (denominator). Results for both the forc-
 441 ings and the non-dimensional numbers at the defined stations are depicted in Figs. (5)
 442 and (6), respectively.

443 Regarding the balance between tidal stresses and baroclinic density gradients (Fig.
 444 6a), tidal stresses are more important ($\log_{10}(\text{Fr}_0) > 0$) throughout the year in the outer
 445 bay, CC, and particularly PC, where the constriction significantly increases flow veloc-
 446 ities, as described in Zarzuelo, López-Ruiz, and Ortega-Sánchez (2018) (Fig. 5a). In con-
 447 trast, baroclinic density gradients are larger in SPC during spring tides. The same oc-
 448 curs in the inner bay in periods such as mid-April, 2013, when high values of baroclinic
 449 density gradients (triggered by both the temperature increases during summer and the
 450 decreases during winter, see Fig. 5b) coincide with the lower the neap tides. The results
 451 also show that during winter and summer, the differences for the baroclinic term are greater,
 452 which reduces the influence of the spring and neap cycles.

453 The results for the stress ratio S_0 (Fig. 6b) show that the trends during the year
 454 are very similar for all stations, although $\log_{10}(S_0)$ ranges around different values depend-
 455 ing on the particular location along the transect. This is explained by the fact that a sin-
 456 gle value of wind conditions was used for the entire bay due to data availability, with tidal
 457 stresses being the only terms that cause differences between stations. At the creeks, where
 458 the influence of friction is greater (Zarzuelo, D'Alpaos, et al., 2019) and tidal stresses are
 459 weaker, wind stresses are more important than tidal stresses by more than 50% of the
 460 year. However, in PC, the tidal stresses are more important than wind stresses during
 461 all the year. Tidal stresses also dominate at the outer and inner bay on spring tides, while
 462 for neap tides the wind stresses are more important if the wind speeds are higher than
 463 10 m/s regardless of the wind direction (e.g. neap tides during mid-June, 2013). How-
 464 ever, SW winds with speeds above 6 m/s make wind stresses be larger than tidal stresses
 465 at the inner bay, even for spring tides (e.g. spring tides in late March, May and late July).

466 The above results show that hydrodynamics within the creeks are not dominated
 467 by tidal stresses during an important part of the year; to check whether wind stresses
 468 or baroclinic density gradients are the main drivers of the flow in these areas, the Wed-
 469 derburn number was applied. The results in Fig. (6c) show that wind stresses prevail
 470 ($\log_{10}(W) > 0$) over baroclinic density gradients in CC almost all year around, even
 471 in summer when these gradients are higher. In SPC, the importance of wind stresses and

Figure 4. Results of the EOF analysis performed for temperature (a) and salinity (b): 1) reconstruction of the data using the first EOF (\bar{e}_1), 2) values of \bar{e}_1 along the bay transect; and 3) temporal distribution of the scores Z_1 (blue) and non-dimensional evaporation

472 baroclinic density gradients alternate, depending on the particular wind conditions and
 473 density gradients (Fig. 5b-c). Only during spring and autumn, when water temperature
 474 and density gradients are lower, wind stresses are clearly larger in this station. During
 475 these seasons, a similar behavior is observed in all stations.

476 Non-dimensional analysis of the momentum balance reveals that hydrodynamics
 477 in basins without creeks is generally driven by tidal stresses, especially in the constric-
 478 tion of the bay (PC), where the effects of tidal stresses increase significantly, being the
 479 largest forcing during the complete year. Only in the inner bay, where tidal flows decrease
 480 as the ocean tide spreads along this basin due to cross-sectional widening, can baroclinic
 481 density gradients prevail for neap tides in summer, where temperature and density gra-
 482 dients along the bay are higher (Fig. 3). In contrast, in SPC both wind stresses and baro-
 483 clinic density gradients can often be the largest forcings, while in CC only wind stresses
 484 can surpass the tidal stresses as they are reduced by the effects of bottom friction (Zaruelo,
 485 D’Alpaos, et al., 2019).

486 There are important differences regarding the effects of wind and density gradients
 487 between CC and SPC. In CC, wind stresses play a more important role than in SPC,
 488 as they are the only forcing which is larger than tidal stresses for some periods of time.
 489 This is due to the alignment of the creeks, which are oriented more parallel to the main
 490 wind directions in SPC, increasing the fetch for the along-transect dynamics and, there-
 491 fore, the role of wind in the hydrodynamics, even when the wind conditions are similar
 492 in both areas. As for the baroclinic density gradients, they are more important in SPC,
 493 since this system is a connection of the bay with the open ocean and density gradients
 494 are higher, while these gradients are attenuated in CC due to their location between the
 495 inner bay and SPC.

496 3.2 The role of waves

497 To quantify the role of waves in density, temperature and salinity distributions, the
 498 differences between the results for S_1 and S_2 (section 2.2.3) were quantified (Fig. 7). The
 499 maximum differences were 3 g/m^3 , 0.45°C and 0.025 psu , corresponding to 50%, 2.7%
 500 and 1.7% of their maximum variability for S_1 (Fig. 3), respectively; although the changes
 501 in salinity and temperature are relatively low, the variations in water density are of the
 502 same order of magnitude as the variations found for S_1 (Fig. 3). These variations are
 503 concentrated close to the connections of the bay with open sea, where waves play a larger
 504 role. Temporal variations are higher in summer, when waves promote mixing, increase
 505 salinity and reduce temperature thus increasing water density. This effect is emphasized
 506 for Southern incoming waves.

507 These results indicate that waves can have a relatively important impact in the hy-
 508 drodynamics of the outer bay and the connection of SPC to the open sea, although changes
 509 in the density due to the variations in the suspended sediment concentrations can be sim-
 510 ilar or even more important. Furthermore, their role in the biogeochemical processes of
 511 the bay, including changes in the metabolic rates (Burgos et al., 2018), is very limited
 512 due to the reduced temperature variations. Although the analysis of the EOFs was re-
 513 peated for S_2 and then compared with S_1 to explore the mechanism that triggers the
 514 temporal changes in salinity and temperature, no conclusive explanation was found.

515 The role that waves play in the momentum balance equation was analyzed by means
 516 of the value of S_w at the defined stations (Fig. 6d). Since this non-dimensional param-
 517 eter depends on the radiation stress gradients (Fig. 5d), which in turn depends on wave
 518 height gradients, CC was excluded from the analysis because waves at this location are
 519 negligible, even though the wave propagation model considered wave generation and growth
 520 by wind. The results for the other four stations are shown in Fig. (6d). In PC, Inner and
 521 SPC, radiation stress gradients are very low compared to tidal stresses, regardless of wave
 522 conditions, and the latter are clearly larger during all the year. However, in Outer lo-

Figure 5. Tidal stresses (a); baroclinic pressure gradients (b); wind stresses (c); and radiation stress gradients (d) for Outer (blue), PC (red), Inner (yellow), CC (purple) and SPC (green) locations.

Figure 6. Logarithm (\log_{10}) distribution of internal tidal Froude number Fr_0 (a); stress ratio S_0 (b); Wedderburn number W (c); and wave stress ratio S_w (d) for Outer (blue), PC (red), Inner (yellow), CC (purple) and SPC (green) locations.

Figure 7. Density (a), salinity (b) and temperature (c) variations along the bay transect when waves are considered. Positive values indicate an increase due to waves. Horizontal and vertical axes represent date and distance to the main bay inlet, respectively. Panel d) shows the wave height (blue line) and wave direction (orange line) measured in buoy 2342 (Fig. 1c).

Figure 8. Percentage of time in which each of the forcings considered prevails along the transect: a) tidal stresses (blue); b) baroclinic density gradients (red); c) wind stresses (yellow); and d) wave stresses (purple).

523 cation radiation stress gradients are similar to the tidal stresses, although waves are larger
 524 than tidal stresses ($\log_{10}(S_w) < 0$) at neap tides or moderate spring tides (e.g. mid-
 525 June, 2013). It can be concluded that waves in basins of complex bays can play a sig-
 526 nificant role in flow currents, and therefore in temperature and salinity distributions, es-
 527 pecially in outer basins facing the open ocean.

528 The results for the momentum balance considering tidal stresses, baroclinic den-
 529 sity gradients, wind stresses and also wave stresses are summarized in Fig. (8), where
 530 the prevalence of each of these forcings along the transect is presented. This prevalence
 531 is defined as the percentage of time when a particular term of the momentum balance
 532 equation is the largest during the simulated year. Results show that waves are clearly
 533 important in the outer bay and up to 6 km along the transect. However, the influence
 534 of the radiation stress gradients is negligible along PC, the inner bay and CC. In SPC,
 535 waves can be very often the prevailing forcing during the last 2 km, which corresponds
 536 to the connection of the creeks with the open ocean. In this area, the influence of the
 537 waves decreases much more rapidly as the tidal wave propagates in the creeks due to their
 538 geometry, which protects the creek channels from the wave action. A maximum is found
 539 near Inlet 2 due to the increased gradients of radiation stresses induced by wave break-
 540 ing in the creek entrance. Fig. (8) also shows that tidal stresses are the most important
 541 forcing during the majority of the year in Outer and PC, being the largest term. As pre-
 542 viously described, wind stresses are the main forcing at the creeks, specially at CC, whereas
 543 at the inner bay the prevalence of tidal stresses, baroclinic density gradients and wind
 544 stresses is similar.

545 The variations in Fr_0 , S_0 and W are evaluated comparing S_1 and S_2 simulations
 546 to quantify the role of the waves. Fig. (9) represents the differences in the non-dimensional
 547 logarithmic numbers, where positive values indicate that the influence of the numera-
 548 tor increases if the wave action is considered. Circles have been added to periods where
 549 there are changes in the balance between the numerator and the denominator. In ad-
 550 dition, the differences for tidal stresses and baroclinic density gradients are also shown
 551 (Fig. 9d and e); for the former, the differences are driven by the effect of waves forces
 552 on flow velocities in the momentum equation, while the latter are due to variations in
 553 temperature and salinity due to the presence of waves (Fig. 7).

554 Similarly to the results for S_w , no significant changes were found for CC. Although
 555 variations in the balance between wind stresses and baroclinic density gradients in In-

ner and PC (Fig. 9c) occur, they do not impact the hydrodynamics of these areas, as they are dominated by tidal stresses. However, in Outer and SPC important changes are found for Fr_0 and W (Fig. 9a and c). These changes are triggered by differences in baroclinic density gradients (Fig. 9e) as they are one order of magnitude greater than those for the tidal stresses (Fig. 9d). These variations tend to increase the period in which tidal stresses are more important ($\log_{10}(Fr_0) > 1$) in the outer bay and baroclinic density gradients are more important at the Sancti-Petri creeks ($\log_{10}(Fr_0) < 1$), concentrating in summer when the maximum differences of the baroclinic density gradients are obtained (Fig. 9e). These differences correspond to the periods in which the maximum differences of density, temperature and salinity of the water were found between S_1 and S_2 (Fig. 7). Therefore, even when the effects of waves on these variables are relatively small, they can significantly alter the role of the different terms in the momentum balance in those basins that connect the bay with the open ocean. These variations depend on the characteristics of the basins: while in open basins they tend to increase the flow velocities reducing the effect of density gradients, the opposite occurs in narrow, frictional basins, such as creeks, where waves increase the effects of these density gradients.

4 Conclusions

This work studies the impact of waves and heat-exchange on the hydrodynamics of multi-basin bays. Although the study is performed in Cdiz Bay, a mesotidal bay in Southern Spain, both the methodology used for the analysis and the main findings of this work can be straightforwardly extrapolated to similar bays due to the applicability of the non-dimensional parameter and EOF analyses. In particular, the analysis focuses on tidal stresses, baroclinic density gradients and wind stresses, and the role that waves play in water currents and in the distributions of density, temperature and salinity. The following conclusions highlight:

1. Water density variations along the bay are dominated by temperature gradients, which in turn are closely related to air temperature; its distribution has seasonal and fortnightly periodicities triggered mainly by air temperature and spring/neap tidal cycles, respectively. Maximum and minimum temperatures and densities were found in the basins of the bay due to the heat exchange between water and air in shallow waters, with gradients along the bay being clearly lower during autumn and spring. Tidal stresses dominate most of the year in the open basins, while in the inner basin, baroclinic density gradients dominate at neap tides during summer, when density gradients along the bay are higher. In contrast, wind stresses and baroclinic density gradients often dominate in the creeks since tidal stresses are reduced by the effects of bottom friction.
2. Waves promote small changes in water temperature and salinity, limiting their impact in the biogeochemical processes in the bay. The variations are concentrated in areas close to the connection between the bay and open sea during the summer, when waves promote mixing, increase salinity and reduce temperature, with the consequent increase in water density. These wave-induced variations in water density between wave and non-wave simulations reach up to 50% of the difference between their minimum and maximum values when all forcings are considered, triggering baroclinic density gradients deviations in the basins that are directly connected to open sea. These deviations frequently increase the importance of tidal stresses in low frictional basins ($\log_{10}(Fr_0) > 0$), while increase the baroclinic density gradients at narrow ($\log_{10}(Fr_0) < 0$), highly frictional channels such as creek systems.
3. In this work, the wave stress ratio S_w is presented, a novel non-dimensional parameter to assess the balance between the tidal and waves stresses. The results show that in the open basin directly connected to the open sea, wave stresses can be the largest forcing at neap or moderate spring tides, which implies that waves

Figure 9. Differences between the simulations S_1 and S_2 in the logarithm (\log_{10}) distributions of internal tidal Froude number Fr_0 (a); stress ratio S_0 (b); Wedderburn number W (c); tidal stresses (d) and baroclinic pressure gradients (e) for Outer, PC, Inner, CC and SPC locations. Circles indicate periods of relevant changes of some terms compared to others.

608 in the outer basins of bays that are not significantly protected from wave action
 609 play an importante role in flow currents, and therefore in temperature and salini-
 610 ty distributions. However, the influence of wave stresses decreases rapidly as the
 611 waves spread into the bay. A similar behavior is observed for a creek system di-
 612 rectly connected to the open sea, although due its narrow geometry, the influence
 613 of waves in this area is very sensitive to wave breaking.

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